

LEARNERS' ATTITUDE AND SELF-EFFICACY TOWARDS ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AT MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY – SULU

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10804845>

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the extent of learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning in terms of emotional aspects, cognitive aspects, and behavioral aspects during the School Year 2023-2024. With 100 samples taken through stratified sampling method, and with the use of weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, One-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r , this study reveals the following findings: 1) Of the 100 student-respondents, mostly are female within the range of 19-21 years old, who are mostly enrolled as fourth year level; 2) On the average, there is high extent of learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of emotional aspects, cognitive aspects, and behavioral aspects; 3) On the average, there is high level of learners' self-efficacy towards English language learning; 4) Generally, variables gender, age, and year level do not significantly mediate in ways how students assessed the learners' attitude towards English language; 5) Generally, variables gender, age, and year level do not significantly mediate in ways how students assessed the level of learners' self-efficacy towards English language; 6) Generally, the group student-respondents who perceived the learners' attitude towards English language learning as Agree or with High Extent may probably be the same group of teachers who perceived the level of learners' self-efficacy towards English language learning as Agree or with High Extent, respectively; 7) This study seems to support Bandura (1986) Social Learning Theory which asserts that learning takes place via observation, imitation, and modeling, and is impacted by variables including attention, motivation, attitudes, and emotions. The

theory also explains how the learning process is influenced by the interaction between cognitive and environmental factors.

Keywords: *learners' attitude, self-efficacy, English language learning, Mindanao State University-Sulu*

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, there is a significant need for individuals to learn and possess the ability to communicate effectively in English across different domains. English language proficiency has become a crucial skill in meeting this demand. Hence, it is crucial to understand deeper learners' attitudes and self-efficacy towards English language learning, as these psychological factors have a substantial impact on learners' motivation and achievements in the process of acquiring the language.

The impact of attitudes towards language learning on learners' achievement and involvement has been widely acknowledged (Dörnyei, 2005). They influence learners' attitudes and feelings towards the language, affecting their drive, diligence, and perseverance in language learning activities. Higher levels of motivation and drive to achieve proficiency have been associated with positive attitudes towards English learning (Gardner, 1985). In contrast, unfavorable attitudes can obstruct the advancement of learners and discourage their inclination to actively participate in language learning (Dörnyei, 2005). Gaining insight into learners' attitudes towards the process of learning the English language is crucial for identifying possible obstacles and developing successful approaches to promote favorable attitudes and increase motivation.

Self-efficacy, a concept introduced by Bandura (1977), pertains to an individual's confidence in their ability to effectively carry out particular tasks. Self-efficacy beliefs have a significant impact on predicting learners' academic performance in the context of language learning (Wigfield & Eccles, 2000). Individuals with a heightened sense of self-efficacy exhibit confidence, perseverance, and a readiness to exert themselves when undertaking language learning tasks, leading to improved language proficiency outcomes (Bandura, 1977). Gaining an understanding of learners' self-efficacy beliefs regarding English language learning can offer valuable insights into how to assist learners in cultivating confidence and resilience throughout their language learning process. In the study of Tahmassian and Moghadam (2011), in the state of student's who have lower self-efficacy, struggles in mental health concerning emotional problems and social problems will likely to occur, which then results to hamper English language learning.

Although there have been numerous studies that have individually explored attitudes and self-efficacy in language learning, there is a scarcity of research that has examined how these two factors are interconnected and how they collectively impact the outcomes of English language learning. Learner's attitudes and self-efficacy are two critical factors that significantly influence the learning process and subsequent English language learning. By investigating learner's attitude on the area of emotional aspect, cognitive aspect, behavioral aspect and the level of learner's efficacy, it will provide valuable insights into the mechanisms that underpin knowledge towards effective English language learning.

This research aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the intricate connections between learners' attitudes and self-efficacy, and how these psychological factors influence their English language learning. By delving into the mechanisms through which learner's attitude and self-efficacy influences individuals' decision-making processes and actions, this study seeks to contribute to a better understanding of the underlying factors that determine one's confidence in their ability to succeed.

Statement of the Problem

This study examines the learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning. Specifically, it attempts to find answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents, specifically in terms of:
 - 1.1.1 age
 - 1.1.2 gender;
 - 1.1.3 year level?
2. What is the learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of:
 - 2.1.1 emotional aspects;
 - 2.1.2 cognitive aspects; and
 - 2.1.3 behavioral aspects
3. What is the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning?
4. Is there a significant difference in learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of:
 - 4.1.1 age;
 - 4.1.2 gender; and
 - 4.1.3 year level?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of:
 - 5.1.1 age;
 - 5.1.2 gender; and
 - 5.1.3 year level?
6. Is there a significant correlation between learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, research locale, respondents of the study, sampling design, data gathering procedure, research instrument, validity and reliability, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

This study used descriptive research design. Salaria (2012) stated in his study entitled "Meaning of the Term- Descriptive Survey Research Method" that according to

Aggarwal (2008) descriptive research is concerned with the interpretation and description of prominent concepts gathered regarding various situations.

Research Locale

The setting of the study was conducted at Mindanao State University – Sulu particularly at the College of Education. It is located at Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study consist of students enrolled in the Bachelor of Secondary Education program, specializing in English, at the College of Education, Mindanao State University - Sulu, during the academic year 2023-2024.

Figure 1.2
Distribution of the Respondents

Year Level	Population	Frequency
1 st Year	75	21
2 nd Year	80	26
3 rd Year	78	24
4 th Year	98	29
TOTAL	331	100

Sampling Design

In this study, stratified random sampling design was utilized. Mason et al. (2003) in order to implement stratified random sampling, a population is subdivided into strata or subgroups according to particular characteristics or variables. Similar-looking subsets of the population are represented by each stratum.

In other words, with stratified random sampling, the target population is divided into separate subgroups, or strata, based on certain traits. The sample size is set for each stratum, and people are chosen at random within each stratum using techniques such as simple random sampling. This process makes sure that the sample is a good representation of the whole population. It also gives a more accurate picture of the population by taking into account differences between the subgroups. Researchers can draw valid conclusions about the whole community from the samples they choose from each stratum by using this design.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before gathering the data needed, the researcher presented the survey questionnaire to the research adviser for modification purposes. Afterwards, the researcher then attached the modified survey questionnaire to the letter that was sent to the two (2) research panelists for validation purposes.

Upon approval to start launching the said modified survey questionnaire, the researcher sent letters to the following: Firstly, the researcher sent letter to the Chancellor, Mindanao State University – Sulu to get a consent to conduct the said study in one of the colleges of the said prestigious institution. Secondly, the researcher sent letter to the Dean, College of Education of Mindanao State University – Sulu to get a permission to conduct the study on the said prestigious department. Lastly, the researcher provided letter to the students who served as the respondents of the study.

The modified survey questionnaire was launched on the first semester of school year 2023-2024. The researcher expected that the retrieval of the said survey questionnaire will not be less than 90 percent.

Research Instrument

In this research, two (2) adopted survey questionnaires were used as part of the research instrument of this study.

This research survey questionnaire was divided into three parts. The first part contains the demographic profile of the respondents of the study. The second part of the survey questionnaire was adopted from the survey administered by Abidin et al. (2012) in his research study. And the last part of the survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Torres and Alieto (2019) in the Philippines, which was patterned from the surveys administered by Clement and Kruidenier (1983), Clement et al. (1994), and Ely (1986) in foreign settings.

The following 5-point Likert Scale was used in the analysis and interpretation of the data collected from the respondents.

Figure 1.3

Rating Scale and Intervals with the Verbal Description

Figure 1.3 was used to determine the learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of the following: emotional aspects, cognitive aspects and behavioral aspects.

Rating Scale	Rating Interval	Verbal Description
1	1.0-1.49	Strongly Agree
2	1.5-2.49	Agree

3	2.5-3.49	Uncertain
4	3.5-4.49	Disagree
5	4.5-5.0	Strongly Disagree

Figure 1.4

Rating Scale and Intervals with the Verbal Description

Figure 1.4 was used to find out the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning.

Rating Scale	Rating Interval	Verbal Description
1	1.0-1.49	Highly Confident
2	1.5-2.49	Confident
3	2.5-3.49	Moderately Confident
4	3.5-4.49	Less Confident
5	4.5-5.0	Not Confident

Validity and Reliability

In this study, the researcher will adopt two survey questionnaires to examine Learners' Attitude and Self-Efficacy Towards English Language Learning. Korb (2012) emphasizes that a researcher is not required to collect validity evidence when the instrument is adopted, as the findings and conclusions of reliability and validity research studies that have been performed on that instrument can be applied to on his/her study.

However, to suit its applicability to the local settings, these questionnaires were subjected for perusal to two panel of experts from the faculty member of the school of graduate studies of Sulu State College.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The computer application SPSS was used by the researcher to assist in the calculations made using the collected data. The appropriate statistical tools were applied to the following:

1. To determine the demographic profile of the respondents Frequency and Percentage were used.
2. To determine the learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of emotional aspects, cognitive aspects and behavioral aspects Weighted Mean were utilized.
3. To find out the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning Weighted Mean were also employed.

4. To examine if there is a significant difference in learners' attitude towards English language learning, T-test was used when the data are classified in terms of gender; and One Way ANOVA was utilized when the data are classified in terms of age and year level.
5. To investigate if there is a significant difference in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning, T-test was employed when the data are classified in terms of gender; and One Way ANOVA was used when the data are classified in terms of age and year level.
6. To assess if there is a significant correlation between learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was utilized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section deals with the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the data obtained for this study. Specifically, it also presents students' demographic profiles in terms of gender, age, and year level; the learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning; significant difference in the learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning; and the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning in the context of emotional aspects, cognitive aspects, and behavioral aspects.

Based upon proper scoring and statistical treatments of data gathered for this study, the following are the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results which correspond to each of the research questions:

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of gender

Gender	Number of Students	Percent
Male	44	44.0%
Female	56	56.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 44 (44.0%) are male and 56 (56.0%) are female. This means that, more than one-half of the student-respondents involved in this study are female which is a bit higher in number than male respondents. This result implies that female respondents constitute the majority in number than their male counterpart for the Academic Year 2023-2024.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of age

Age	Number of Students	Percent
18 years old & below	5	5.0%
19-21 years old	53	53.0%
22-24 years old	37	37.0%
25 years old & above	5	5.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of age. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 5 (5.0%) are within 18 years old & below of age bracket, 53 (53.0%) are within 19-21 years old, 37 (37.0%) are within 22-24 years old, and 5 (5.0%) are within 25 years old & above. This means that, more than one-half of the student-respondents involved in this study are within the age range of 19-21 years old.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile of learner-respondents in terms of year level

Year Level	Number of Respondents	Percent
First year	21	21.0%
Second year	26	26.0%
Third year	24	24.0%
Fourth year	29	29.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of year level. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 21 (21.0%) are first year, 26 (26.0%) are second year, 24 (24.0%) are third year, and 29 (29.0%) are fourth year level. This means that, all year levels are represented by nearly the same number of students but many from them are fourth year level.

Table 2.1 Learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of emotional aspects

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I feel proud when studying English language.	4.5600	.57419	Strongly Agree
2	I feel excited when I communicate in English with others.	4.2600	.73333	Agree
3	I don't get anxious when I have to answer a question in my English class.	3.5000	.96922	Agree
4	Studying foreign languages like English is enjoyable	4.2600	.78650	Agree
5	To be inquisitive makes me study English well.	3.9800	.77824	Agree
6	Studying English makes me have good emotions (feelings).	3.9800	.81625	Agree
7	I prefer studying in my mother tongue rather than any other foreign language.	3.0300	1.1845	Undecided

8	I enjoy doing activities in English.	4.1600	.72083	Agree
9	I do not like studying English.	1.8100	1.1780	Disagree
10	I wish I could speak English fluently.	4.7500	.68718	Strongly Agree
11	I am interested in studying English.	4.7500	.55732	Strongly Agree
12	Studying English subject makes me feel more confident.	4.4000	.82878	Agree
13	To be honest, I really have little interest in my English class.	3.1300	1.3382	Undecided
14	Knowing English is an important goal in my life.	4.4200	.66939	Agree
15	I look forward to the time I spend in English class.	4.2000	.71067	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		3.9460	.35260	Agree

Legend: (5)4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree (SA); (4) 3.50–4.49= Agree (A); (3) 2.50–3.49= Undecided (U); (2) 1.50–2.49=Disagree (D); (1) 1.00 – 1.49= Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.1 shows the learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of emotional aspects. Under this category, students' assessment has total weighted mean score of 3.9460 with standard deviation of .35260 which is rated as **Agree** or with **High Level**. This result indicates that student-respondents involved in this study expressed that they have high level of feelings and emotions towards English language learning. That is, they feel proud when studying English language excited to communicate in English with others.

Specifically, from among the items under this category, student-respondents rated as Agree or with High level the following items: "I feel excited when I communicate in English with others", "I don't get anxious when I have to answer a question in my English class", "Studying foreign languages like English is enjoyable", "To be inquisitive makes me study English well", "Studying English makes me have good emotions (feelings)", "I enjoy doing activities in English", "Studying English subject makes me feel more confident", "Knowing English is an important goal in my life", and "I look forward to the time I spend in English class".

Table 2.2 Learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of cognitive aspects

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Studying English is important because it will make me more educated.	4.4242	.82178	Agree
2	Being good at English will help me study other subjects well.	4.5354	.78653	Strongly Agree
3	I have more knowledge and more understanding when studying English.	4.1616	.75196	Agree
4	I like my English class so much; I look forward to studying more English in the future.	4.5051	.62879	Strongly Agree
5	Studying English helps me getting new information in which I can link to my previous knowledge.	4.4646	.61134	Agree
6	I cannot summarize the important points in the English subject content by myself.	3.1010	1.1649	Undecided
7	Frankly, I study English just to pass the exams.	2.3838	1.2264	Undecided
8	In my opinion, people who speak more than one language are very knowledgeable.	4.0101	1.0832	Agree

9	Studying English helps me communicate in English effectively.	4.3939	.72588	Agree
10	I cannot apply the knowledge from English subject in my real life.	2.3434	1.2051	Disagree
11	Studying English makes me able to create new thoughts.	4.2727	.72588	Agree
12	I am able to think and analyze the content in English language.	3.9697	.73477	Agree
13	I am not satisfied with my performance in the English subject.	3.3030	1.0147	Undecided
14	In my opinion, English language is difficult and complicated to learn.	3.3939	.92381	Undecided
15	English subject has the content that covers many fields of knowledge.	4.1818	.71946	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		3.8296	.39832	Agree

Legend: (5)4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree (SA); (4) 3.50–4.49= Agree (A); (3) 2.50–3.49= Undecided (U); (2) 1.50–2.49=Disagree (D); (1) 1.00 – 1.49= Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.2 shows the learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of cognitive aspects. Under this category, students' assessment has total weighted mean score of 3.8296 with standard deviation of .39832 which is rated as **Agree** or with **High Level**. This result indicates that student-respondents involved in this study expressed that they have high level aspects of attitudes relative to their beliefs, thoughts or viewpoints about English language learning.

Specifically, from among the items under this category, student-respondents rated as Agree or with High level the following items: "Studying English is important because it will make me more educated", "I have more knowledge and more understanding when studying English", "Studying English helps me getting new information in which I can link to my previous knowledge", "In my opinion, people who speak more than one language are very knowledgeable", "Studying English helps me communicate in English effectively", "Studying English makes me able to create new thoughts", and "I am able to think and analyze the content in English language".

Table 2.3 Learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of behavioral aspects

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Speaking English anywhere makes me feel worried.	3.0900	1.0356	Undecided
2	Studying English helps me to have good relationships with friends.	3.6800	.91982	Agree
3	I like to give opinions during English lessons.	3.7200	.92201	Agree
4	I am able to make myself pay attention during studying English.	4.1200	.70036	Agree
5	When I hear a student in my class speaking English well, I like to practice speaking with him/her.	4.3500	.71598	Agree
6	Studying English makes me have more confidence in expressing myself.	4.1500	.78335	Agree

7	Studying English helps me to improve my personality.	4.1800	.78341	Agree
8	I put off my English homework as much as possible.	3.3900	.95235	Undecided
9	I am not relaxed whenever I have to speak in my English class.	3.0500	1.0576	Undecided
10	I feel embarrassed to speak English in front of other students.	3.1900	1.1694	Undecided
11	I like to practice English the way native speakers do.	4.2400	.76700	Agree
12	I wish I could have many English-speaking friends.	4.3800	.76251	Agree
13	When I miss the class, I never ask my friends or teachers for the homework on what has been taught.	2.3900	1.2300	Disagree
14	I do not feel enthusiastic to come to class when the English is being thought.	2.4100	1.2640	Disagree
15	I do not pay any attention when my English teacher is explaining the lesson.	1.8800	1.2083	Disagree
Total Weighted Mean		3.4813	.42625	Undecided

Legend: (5)4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree (SA); (4) 3.50–4.49= Agree (A); (3) 2.50–3.49= Undecided (U); (2) 1.50–2.49=Disagree (D); (1) 1.00 – 1.49= Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.3 shows the learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of behavioral aspects. Under this category, students' assessment has total weighted mean score of 3.4813 with standard deviation of .42625 which is rated as **Undecided** or with **Moderate Level**. This result indicates that student-respondents involved in this study expressed that they have moderate level aspects of attitudes relative to their behaviors and reactions towards English language learning.

Specifically, from among the items under this category, student-respondents rated as Undecided or with Moderate level the following items: "Speaking English anywhere makes me feel worried", "I put off my English homework as much as possible", "I am not relaxed whenever I have to speak in my English class", "I am not relaxed whenever I have to speak in my English class", and "I feel embarrassed to speak English in front of other students".

Table 3. Level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Listen to and understand the main ideas of a televised public service announcement in English.	3.9900	.84680	Confident
2	Listen to and understand the details of short conversations in English.	4.2000	.71067	Confident
3	Listen to and understand the main ideas of a short-televised news report in English.	4.0500	.70173	Confident
4	Listen to and comprehend the details of conversations in English documentaries, films, songs and television programs.	4.0200	.73828	Confident
5	Listen to and comprehend the idea given in a lecture delivered by an English speaker.	4.1700	.71145	Confident

6	Recite in English class fluently.	3.3000	1.0298	Moderately Confident
7	Deliver report using English as the medium.	3.5200	.79747	Confident
8	Deliver solo performances like oration, and declamation and some modes of public speaking.	3.2500	1.0766	Moderately Confident
9	Read and understand the main ideas of print ads in English.	3.8300	.79207	Confident
10	Read and understand the main ideas of a short English article.	3.9700	.67353	Confident
11	Read and understand the news articles and features in an English newspaper.	3.8600	.80428	Confident
12	Read and understand instructions in manuals of gadgets or appliances.	3.8800	.84423	Confident
13	Read and understand the details of a poem, essay, short story and novels in English.	4.0800	.80000	Confident
14	Write a business letter in English.	3.5300	.98939	Confident
15	Write a short narrative with correct English.	3.5700	.98734	Confident
16	Write a long narrative with correct English.	3.5100	1.0492	Confident
17	Engage in an informal conversation using English.	3.6300	.99143	Confident
18	Communicate ideas in English clearly and correctly.	3.5100	1.0395	Confident
19	Engage in academic discussion using English language.	3.6100	1.0039	Confident
20	Communicate ideas effectively and efficiently in English written discourse.	3.4300	.95616	Moderately Confident
Total Weighted Mean		3.7455	.58409	Confident

Legend: (5)4.50-5.00= Highly Confident; (4) 3.50–4.49= Confident; (3) 2.50–3.49= Moderately Confident; (2) 1.50–2.49=Less Confident; (1) 1.00 – 1.49= Not Confident

Table 3 shows the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning. Under this category, students' assessment has total weighted mean score of 3.7455 with standard deviation of .58409 which is rated as **Confident**. This result indicates that student-respondents involved in this study expressed confidence that they have the ability to successfully learn the English language.

Specifically, from among the items under this category, student-respondents rated as Confident level the following items: "Listen to and understand the main ideas of a televised public service announcement in English", "Listen to and understand the details of short conversations in English", "Listen to and understand the main ideas of a short-televised news report in English", "Listen to and comprehend the details of conversations in English documentaries, films, songs and television programs", "Read and understand the main ideas of print ads in English", "Read and understand the main ideas of a short English article", "Read and understand the news articles and features in an English newspaper", "Read and understand instructions in manuals of gadgets or appliances", and "Read and understand the details of a poem, essay, short story and novels in English".

Table 4.1 Differences in learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of gender

VARIABLES	Grouping	Mean	S. D.	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Emotional Aspects	Male	3.9273	.31263	-.03515	-.489	.626	Not Significant
	Female	3.9624	.38656				
Cognitive Aspects	Male	3.8212	.43104	-.01212	-.148	.882	Not Significant
	Female	3.8333	.37685				
Behavioral Aspects	Male	3.5348	.42977	.09970	1.154	.252	Not Significant
	Female	3.4352	.42530				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 4.1 shows the differences in learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that the values of mean differences of categories subsumed under the learners' attitude towards English language learning are not significant at alpha .05. This means that male and female student-respondents do not differ in their perceptions towards the learners' attitude towards English language learning. This finding implies that being a male student-respondent may not necessarily put him in vantage point towards perceiving the learners' attitude towards English language learning than his female counterpart, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has indeed no significant influence in the ways how student-respondents assess the learners' attitude towards English language learning. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of gender" accepted.

Table 4.2 Differences in the learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Emotional Aspects	Between Groups	.295	3	.098	.787	.504	Not Significant
	Within Groups	12.013	96	.125			
	Total	12.308	99				
Cognitive Aspects	Between Groups	.232	3	.077	.480	.697	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.316	95	.161			
	Total	15.549	98				
Behavioral Aspects	Between Groups	1.067	3	.356	2.017	.117	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.921	96	.176			
	Total	17.987	99				

*Significant alpha .05

Table 4.2 presents the differences in the learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of age. It can be gleaned from this table that the values of F-ratios and *P*-values of all the sub-categories subsumed under the learners' attitude towards English language learning are not significant at alpha .05. This means that even though student-respondents vary in age range, yet they do not differ in their perceptions towards the learners' attitude towards English language learning. This result implies that being a 25 years old & above may not necessarily put a student-respondent in vantage point towards perceiving the learners' attitude towards English language learning than those students within 18 years old & below, 19-20, and 21-24 years old, or vice versa.

Nonetheless, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant mediation in ways how student-respondents assess the learners' attitude towards English language learning. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of age" is accepted.

Table 4.3 Differences in the learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of year level

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Emotional Aspects	Between Groups	.552	3	.184	1.503	.219	Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.756	96	.122			
	Total	12.308	99				
Cognitive Aspects	Between Groups	1.431	3	.477	3.211*	.026	Significant
	Within Groups	14.117	95	.149			
	Total	15.549	98				
Behavioral Aspects	Between Groups	1.081	3	.360	2.047	.112	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.906	96	.176			
	Total	17.987	99				

*Significant alpha .05

Table 4.3 presents the differences in the learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of year level. It can be gleaned from this table that, except for "Cognitive Aspects" the values of F-ratios and *P*-values of all other sub-categories subsumed under the learners' attitude towards English language learning are not significant at alpha .05. This means that even though student-respondents vary in year level, yet they do not differ in their perceptions towards the learners' attitude towards English language learning. This result implies that being enrolled as fourth year level may not necessarily put a student-respondent in vantage point towards perceiving the learners' attitude towards English language learning than those students enrolled as first year, second year, and third year levels, or vice versa.

Nonetheless, it is safe to say that variable year level has no significant mediation in ways how student-respondents assess the learners' attitude towards English language learning. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in learners' attitude towards English language learning when the data are classified in terms of year level" is accepted.

Table 5.1 Differences in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of gender

VARIABLES		Mean	S. D.	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Learner's Self-Efficacy	Male	3.7591	.53410	.01364	.115	.909	Not Significant
	Female	3.7455	.62578				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 5.1 shows the differences in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that the value of mean difference of level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning is not significant at alpha .05. This means that male and female student-respondents do not differ in their perceptions towards the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning. This finding implies that being a male student-respondent may not necessarily put him in vantage point towards perceiving the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning than his female counterpart, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has indeed no significant influence in the ways how student-respondents assess the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of gender" is accepted.

Table 5.2 Differences in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Learner' Self-Efficacy	Between Groups	.681	3	.227	.659	.580	Not Significant
	Within Groups	33.094	96	.345			
	Total	33.775	99				

*Significant alpha .05

Table 5.2 presents the differences in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of age. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-ratio and *P*-value of the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning is not significant at alpha .05. This means that even though student-respondents vary in age range, yet they do not differ in their perceptions towards the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning. This result implies that being a 25

years old & above may not necessarily put a student-respondent in vantage point towards perceiving the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning than those students within 18 years old & below, 19-20, and 21-24 years old, or vice versa.

Nonetheless, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant mediation in ways how student-respondents assess the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of age" is accepted.

Table 5.3 Differences in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of year level

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Learner' Self-Efficacy	Between Groups	.437	3	.146	.420	.739	Not Significant
	Within Groups	33.338	96	.347			
	Total	33.775	99				

*Significant alpha .05

Table 5.3 presents the differences in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of year level. It can be gleaned from this table that the F-ratio and P-value of the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning is not significant at alpha .05. This means that even though student-respondents vary in year level, yet they do not differ in their perceptions towards the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning. This result implies that being enrolled as a fourth year level may not necessarily put a student-respondent in vantage point towards perceiving the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning than those students enrolled as first year, second year, and third year levels, or vice versa.

Nonetheless, it is safe to say that variable year level has no significant mediation in ways how student-respondents assess the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the level of learners' self-efficacy in English language learning when the data are classified in terms of year level" is accepted.

Table 6. Correlation between learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Learners' Self-Efficacy	Learners' Attitude	.225*	.025	100	Low

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002): 0.0-0.1=Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.30=Low; .3-0.5 0=Moderate; .5-0.7-0=High; .7-0.9= Very High; 0.9-1=Nearly Perfect

Table 6 illustrates the correlation between learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning. It can be gleaned from this table that the computed Pearson Correlation Coefficients (Pearson *r*) between these variables is indeed significant at alpha .05.

Specifically, the degree of correlation between learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning is as follows:

- 1) Low positive correlation between learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning.

These results indicate that the group student-respondents who perceived the learners' attitude towards English language learning as Agree or with High Extent may probably the same group of teachers who perceived the level of learners' self-efficacy towards English language learning as Agree or with High Extent, respectively.

Meanwhile, it is safe to say that, generally the learners' attitude and level of self-efficacy towards English language learning is lowly correlated.

Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant correlation between learners' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning" is rejected.

CONCLUSIONS

This study envisioned to determine the learners' attitude and level of self-efficacy towards English language learning among education students at Mindanao State University – Sulu during the School Year 2023-2024; and the significant differences and correlation among these variables when data are grouped according to gender, age, and year level.

The following are the conclusions made based on the findings of this study:

- 1) Student-respondents involved in this study are adequately represented in terms of gender, age, and year level.
- 2) On the average, there is high extent of learners' attitude towards English language learning in terms of emotional aspects, cognitive aspects, and behavioral aspects.

3) On the average, there is high level of learners' self-efficacy towards English language learning.

4) Generally, variables gender, age, and year level do not significantly mediate in ways how students assessed the learners' attitude towards English language.

5) Generally, variables gender, age, and year level do not significantly mediate in ways how students assessed the level of learners' self-efficacy towards English language.

6) Generally, the group student-respondents who perceived the learners' attitude towards English language learning as Agree or with High Extent may probably the same group of teachers who perceived the level of learners' self-efficacy towards English language learning as Agree or with High Extent, respectively.

7) This study seems to support Bandura (1986) Social Learning Theory which asserts that learning takes place via observation, imitation, and modeling, and is impacted by variables including attention, motivation, attitudes, and emotions. The theory also explains how the learning process is influenced by the interaction between cognitive and environmental factors.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study recommends the following based on the above findings and conclusions:

1) School administrators may formulate programs and policies that geared towards the enhancement of students' attitude and self-efficacy towards English language learning.

2) School administrators may adapt the findings of this study to reinforce the decision-making of the school leadership; and to address issues on student behavior, school improvement plans, and curriculum enhancement.

3) Language teachers may look closely how students' attitude and self-efficacy affects the latter's ability to learn English language and enhancing their English language learning outcomes.

4) English language students may use the outcomes of this research in order to enhance their attitude and self-efficacy towards learning English language.

5) Student-researchers in the field of language learning and teaching are encouraged to replicate this study but to include other variables such as language learning engagement, language learning anxiety, and language attitudes and strategies in some other avenues.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researcher wishes to extend her genuine appreciation and deep gratitude to the individuals who contributed to this study endeavor, particularly the following:

To **Dr. Charisma Ututalum**, the President of SSC, for her constant support in making significant changes in SSC for the betterment of Sulu.

To **Dr. Nelson U. Julhamid**, the Vice President of SSC, the brilliant, kind, and very accommodating adviser, for his ceaseless and untiring effort to offer insightful opinions and recommendations;

to **Dr. Masnona S. Asiri**, the Dean of SSC Graduate School and the chairman of the committee, for her exceptional support, encouragement, and guidance throughout the title and proposal defense;

to **Dr. Abdel Amilhamja**, a member of the defense committee, valuable input, consisting of insightful questions, remarks, and ideas, which greatly contributed to the success of our research;

to **Dr. Nagder J. Abdurahman**, the Chancellor II of MSU-Sulu, for his approval to conduct this research on his prestigious university;

to **Prof. Abdel-Ajim M. Salasain**, Dean of College of Education, MSU-Sulu, for giving consent to conduct this research at his college;

and **MSU-Sulu College of Education students** who wholeheartedly agreed to take part in this research study.

Special note of appreciation is also given to the individuals who provided support to her during the research endeavor. Specifically, the following:

To her beloved father late **Mr. Jumala Jadi Abbas** and her mother **Mrs. Nur-aina Alfad Abbas**, her siblings namely: **Zhalha Jane A. Abbas**, **Al-assan A. Alfad**, **Annie-lizz A. Abbas**, **Radiya A. Abbas**, **Nur-hassan A. Alfad**, and cousin **Nelson R. Ameri** who serves as her inspiration and motivation since then, and who also provided unwavering love, complete support, and boundless understanding that helped her overcome this arduous and challenging journey;

to **Mr. Mohaider J. Kairan**, her husband, who has been there for her through the good times and the bad, and who has also given her his undying love, support, and encouragement;

to her **colleagues and friends**, for giving continuous motivation and sharing several joyful moments amidst challenging days, which greatly enhanced the value of the journey;

Above all, to **Allah (S.W.T.)** for surrounding her with the best people in the world and whose guidance and blessings makes all things possible for the researcher.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

To ensure the compliance of ethical standards in research, the researcher obtained an informed consent from the respondents. Likewise, the researcher assured that anonymity of the respondents and the data gathered are kept confidential.

REFERENCES

- Alieto, E., & Torres, J. (2019). English Learning Motivation and Self-Efficacy of Filipino Senior High School. *The Asian EFL Journal*.
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*.
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self Efficacy The Exercise of Control*. New York: W.H Freeman and Company.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2006). *The Psychology of the Language Learner Individual Differences in Second Language Acquisition*. Routledge.
- Gardner, R. (1985). *Social psychology and second language learning. The role of attitudes and motivation*.
- Korb, K. (2012). *Conducting Educational Research*.
- Mason, R., Gunst, R., & Hess, J. (2003). *Statistical Design and Analysis of Experiments: With Applications to Engineering and Science*.
- Salaria, N. (2012). Meaning of the Term Descriptive Survey Research Method. *International Journal of Transformations in Business Management*.
- Tahmassian, K., & Moghadam, N. (n.d.). Relationship Between Self-Efficacy and Symptoms of Anxiety, Depression, Worry and Social Avoidance in a Normal Sample of Students.
- Wigfield, A., & Eccles, J. (2000). Expectancy–Value Theory of Achievement Motivation. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*.